

A Study of Impact of Bibliotherapeutic Approach on Challenges Faced By Students of Teacher Education Institute

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Abstract

This paper focuses on aspects of bibliotherapy in respect to academic, psychological and social challenges faced by students of Teacher Education Institute. Bibliotherapy is helpful in treating long term mental illness in the form of depression, anxiety, low confidence, phobia, fear, shyness,. Investigator has used qualitative and quantitative methods of study on which this article is based. The result of the experiment is positive and draw inference that bibliotherapy has a positive effect after treatment. Investigator has conducted interview with the TEI students and it is classified that social well being has improved significantly so as self confidence and social interaction has risen up among students. The self help material investigator selected with the help of subject experts in education and Library and Information Science faculty had significant positive result. Investigator adopted methods like discussion, interview, conversation, debate, quiz to open up minds of students. So that they could openly share their challenges, issues, difficulties with the investigator. Bibliotherapy is effective method for psychological well-being. It improves self-confidence and social interaction. From user perspective bibliotherapy is an important tool of improvement.

Introduction

Bibliotherapy is the use of literature to promote psychological well-being , mental health has got significance in recent years. The bibliotherapy concept was known to us since beginning of 21st century. Through bibliotherapeutic activities like reading circle, book club, reading hours, books on wheels projects reading culture get impetus. Bibliotherapy is a quite well researched internationally. For psychological illness it is effective tool. Students suffering from long term anxiety, depression, phobia, shyness take part in bibliotherapeutic activities. These activities were in the form of reading circles, reading clubs have a potential to increase feeling of well-being among student, self-help material are very useful in mental illness problem. Considering the students old reading habits and inclination towards likings of particular genre may help immediately to treat challenges, problem among students. This therapy helps in curing psychological problems but concrete examples of how and how much psychological wellbeing was influenced were not provided(Hodge, Robinson and Davis, 2007) For bibliotherapeutic program students met for three hours twice in a week for 6 months from September till February. Literature was selected by the investigator and with the help of experts from education field. The investigator used conversation, discussion, quiz, reading aloud sessions. All students attended all the sessions enthusiastically. A questionnaire tool was used to get qualitative

data from the students. Five point rating scale was used in this research by investigator. Each questionnaire tool consists of 10 questions. Media influence variable has qualitative data to collect right answers from the students. It was experimental method of study, so pretest and posttest questions were forwarded to students to collect data. All data collected from the samples kept confidential. According to literary choices of students, their liking of reading, their tendency to particular genre were considered while providing literature to them.

Pim Cuijpers conducted considerable research on bibliotherapy, states that bibliotherapy is more successful for participants who are motivated and have significant reading experience.(Cuijpers, 1997). Reading has a curing function. Students were felt that reading was a pathway to their success in life and beating challenges and problems in their life.

Significance of bibliotherapeutic approach

All student participants were enthusiastic while reading sessions. Reading sessions had positive influence on psychological, academic and social well-being of student participant. These particular aspects are important for selection of the literature consciously. Further bibliotherapeutic activity helps in opportunities offered for social interaction

The literature in the bibliotherapeutic treatment.

All student participants expressed their happiness and appreciation of the literature

sessions during and in preparation for reading and conversation sessions.

It is observed that on some occasion student were in difficulty to concentrate during sessions. Literary quality plays a vital role during implementing bibliotherapeutic programme. Brewster points out that several of her informants reported that the act of reading itself was more important than the specific works read in helping them deal with their psychological problems (Brewster,2011)

In a bibliotherapeutic sessions the literature discussions were held, significance of the experts while implementing programme was ensured and significance of bibliotherapeutic activities in relation to other activities were noted.

Bibliotherapeutic Discussions

It is worth to note that aspects of literary discussions most appreciated by students participant. The attitude of the student was expressed in all the interviews. Bibliotherapy promotes changes in the students. Students use reading as a leisure activity. The bibliotherapeutic approach was meaningful to the students and has positive effect on their perception of health and psychological well being. Participant felt better than before. Participants are of the opinion that reading activity can help them prevent a worsening of well-being. Students reacted positively. So it is clear that bibliotherapeutic approach brought change in challenges intensity. Student put forward opinion that because of these bibliotherapeutic treatment they have started more reading. Participants gives feedback that their social interaction has risen up because of social interaction. The findings of this study are student participants have improvement in their challenges. Through bibliotherapeutic sessions self-confidence risen up, shyness has reduced, social skills are improved. Emotional challenges of the students can treat through bibliotherapy.

Statement of the problem

A Study Of Impact Of Bibliotherapeutic Approach On A Challenges Faced By Students Of Teacher Education Institutes.

Objectives

1. To identify the challenges faced by TEI students.
2. To identify the sources of challenges faced by TEI students.
3. To develop a bibliotherapeutic programme and study its effectiveness in the context of academic, psychological and social challenges.
4. To study the effect of bibliotherapeutic approach on academic challenges in context of

difficulties in understanding B.Ed. curriculum and academic procrastination.

5. To study the effect of bibliotherapeutic approach on psychological challenges in context of academic stress and study anxiety.

6. To study the effect of bibliotherapeutic approach on social challenges in context of media influence and family expectations.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of academic challenges in context of difficulties in understanding B.Ed. curriculum and academic procrastination at the pre and post test level.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of psychological challenges in context of academic stress and study anxiety at the pre and post test level.

3. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social challenges in context of media influence and family expectations at the pre and post test level.

Methodology

In the light of objectives and to test the hypotheses of the present study, the researcher adopted experimental method of the study and for data collection questionnaire tool was used.

Statistical Treatment

Arithmetic mean, Standard Deviation, were used.

Results and Interpretation

H1 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of academic challenges in context of difficulties in understanding B.Ed. curriculum and academic procrastination at the pre and post test level.

There exist significant difference in the pre and post test scores of academic challenges. High mean value of the post test in respects of difficulties in understanding B.Ed syllabus and academic procrastination shows that bibliotherapeutic treatment applied was proved successful and outcome was positive.

H2 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of psychological challenges in context of academic stress and study anxiety at the pre and post test level.

There is significant difference in the mean scores of psychological challenges in context of academic stress and study anxiety. There exist significant difference in the pre and post test scores of psychological challenges. High mean value of the post test in respects of academic stress and study anxiety shows that bibliotherapeutic treatment applied was proved successful and outcome was positive.

H3 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social challenges in context of media

influence and family expectations at the pre and post test level.

There is significant difference in the mean scores of social challenges in context of media influence and family expectations. There exist significant difference in the pre and post test scores of psychological challenges. High mean value of the post test in respects of media influence and family expectations shows that bibliotherapeutic treatment applied was proved successful and outcome was positive.

Conclusion

- There is significant Mean difference in academic challenges scores of pre and post level. So bibliotherapeutic programme was proved successful.
- There is significant Mean difference in psychological challenges scores of pre and post level. So bibliotherapeutic programme was proved successful.
- There is significant Mean difference in social challenges scores of pre and post level. So

bibliotherapeutic programme was proved successful.

Suggestions for further research

- The study can be extended to state level.
- Further study can be undertaken considering male, female, student categories.
- Small sample may be taken for more reliable results.

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